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Knowledge, awareness, and practice of zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management among Nigerian-trained nurses studying abroad: A cross-sectional study

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Diarrhoea remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among children under five years globally. Despite World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) recommendations for zinc supplementation alongside oral rehydration salts, implementation gaps persist among healthcare providers. To assess knowledge, awareness, and practice regarding zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management among Nigerian-trained nurses studying abroad. A cross-sectional study was conducted in August-September 2016 among 63 Nigerian-trained nurses at Anglia Ruskin University, United Kingdom. Data were collected using an electronic questionnaire through snowball sampling and analysed using SPSS version 20.0 with Chi-square test to examine associations. Response rate was 96.9% (n=63). Ninety percent of nurses were aware of zinc supplementation, with 63% demonstrating adequate knowledge. Sixty-seven percent reported having used zinc supplements in practice in Nigeria. A significant association was found between knowledge and reported practice ($\chi^2=32.904$, $p<0.001$). Among this sample, awareness of zinc supplementation was high and knowledge was moderate, though practice implementation in Nigeria was below universal levels. The strong knowledge-practice association suggests enhanced training programmes may improve implementation. Findings may not be generalisable to nurses practicing in Nigeria due to sample characteristics.

Key words: Zinc supplementation, childhood diarrhoea, nurses, knowledge, practice, Nigeria, developing countries.

INTRODUCTION

Childhood diarrhoea continues to pose a significant global health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-

income countries. Diarrhoea remains a leading cause of death globally among children under five years of age and

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contributes to nutritional deficiencies, reduced resistance to infections, and impaired growth and development. The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates that approximately 525,000 children under five die from diarrhoea diseases annually, with the majority of these deaths occurring in low- and middle-income nations (WHO, 2023; United Nations Inter-Agency Group for Child Mortality Estimation, 2024). Nigeria faces a substantial burden of childhood diarrhoea, ranking as the third leading cause of death among children under five years and accounting for approximately 16% of all childhood deaths in the country (Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey [NDHS], 2018). The NDHS revealed that while under-five mortality rates declined from 201 deaths per 1,000 live births in 2003 to 128 deaths per 1,000 live births in 2013, the country fell short of achieving the Millennium Development Goal target of 64 deaths per 1,000 live births by 2015 (NDHS, 2018).

Since 2004, the WHO and the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) have recommended zinc supplementation (10 to 20 mg daily for 10 to 14 days) alongside oral rehydration salts (ORS) as the standard treatment for childhood diarrhoea. Despite this, uptake remains inconsistent. Recent studies have highlighted persistent gaps in implementation among healthcare providers in Nigeria and other African countries (Ogundele et al., 2023; Ibrahim et al., 2023). Nurses, as frontline healthcare providers in most healthcare settings, play a crucial role in implementing evidence-based diarrhoea management protocols. This study evaluates the awareness, knowledge, and practice of zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management among Nigerian-trained nurses studying abroad, offering insights into potential barriers and facilitators to the optimal implementation of WHO/UNICEF guidelines. The study specifically focuses on Nigerian-trained nurses pursuing advanced education abroad, representing a subset of the nursing workforce with access to international educational opportunities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Zinc supplementation: Mechanisms and evidence

Zinc is a micronutrient that plays a role in immune system strengthening and regulation of intestinal epithelial cells and can reduce the duration and severity of diarrhoea. Zinc is an essential micronutrient that plays a crucial role in the metabolism of proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, as well as in gene transcription. This micronutrient is critical for numerous physiological processes, including reproduction, immune function, and wound healing. At the cellular level, zinc is indispensable for the normal function of macrophages, neutrophils, natural killer cells, and the complement system (Ali et al., 2024). The therapeutic

mechanisms of zinc in diarrhoea management are multifaceted. Zinc maintains intestinal mucosal integrity, preventing fluid and electrolyte loss during diarrhoea episodes. It also supports immune function by enhancing T-cell proliferation and natural killer cell activity, reducing the risk of secondary infections. Additionally, zinc supplementation helps restore depleted zinc stores that occur during diarrhoea episodes, preventing zinc deficiency and its associated complications (Ali et al., 2024).

Clinical evidence prior to 2016

Multiple systematic reviews and meta-analyses published before 2016 provided compelling evidence for zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea. Studies demonstrated that zinc supplementation reduced the duration of acute diarrhoea episodes and decreased the severity of illness. The WHO recommendation for 20 mg daily zinc supplementation for 10 to 14 days was based on trials showing significant clinical benefits, though some studies reported increased vomiting as an adverse effect at this dosage level. Research by Bhandari et al. (2008) demonstrated the effectiveness of zinc supplementation plus oral rehydration salts compared with oral rehydration salts alone in primary care settings. Other studies confirmed zinc's role in reducing both the duration and severity of diarrhoea episodes across diverse populations and settings. The significant reduction in child mortality due to diarrhoea has been primarily attributed to the use of oral rehydration solutions, continuous feeding, and zinc supplementation.

Healthcare provider knowledge and practice gaps

Several studies conducted before and during 2016 identified significant gaps in healthcare provider knowledge and implementation of zinc supplementation guidelines. Research showed that uptake of evidence-based interventions remained slow in developing countries, with many children suffering from diarrhoea not receiving appropriate treatment.

A study by Omuemu et al. (2012) found that while 66.1% of healthcare providers in Nigeria were aware of zinc supplementation, only 35% included it in their diarrhoea management protocols. Similarly, research in Ethiopia reported in 2015 that only 58% of primary healthcare workers demonstrated adequate knowledge about zinc benefits in diarrhoea management (Seifu et al., 2024; Ibrahim et al., 2023). These findings highlighted the persistent gap between evidence-based recommendations and clinical implementation.

Research by Esezobor et al. (2011) among Nigerian paediatric doctors revealed variable knowledge and

acceptance of zinc therapy, with better knowledge among those who had received formal training in updated diarrhoea management protocols. Studies from India and other developing countries documented similar challenges with guideline implementation, often complicated by continued inappropriate antibiotic prescription for viral diarrhoea illnesses (Ogundele et al., 2023). More recent international studies have revealed persistent challenges in zinc implementation. A multi-country analysis from sub-Saharan Africa covering 2007-2018 found that adherence to WHO recommendations remained suboptimal despite increased awareness (Deichsel et al., 2023). Studies from Ethiopia in 2024 documented that zinc utilisation among children with acute diarrhoea varied significantly across regions, with factors such as maternal education, previous zinc exposure, and healthcare access playing crucial roles in adoption rates (Seifu et al., 2024). An analysis of Demographic and Health Survey data from 23 low- and middle-income countries demonstrated positive trends toward wider zinc adoption between 2010 and 2020, though substantial gaps remained (Karlsson et al., 2024).

Barriers to implementation

Multiple barriers were identified in the literature as contributing to suboptimal zinc supplementation practices. Knowledge gaps and insufficient understanding of zinc's mechanisms and benefits represented a primary barrier. Supply chain issues resulted in inconsistent availability of zinc supplements in many healthcare facilities. Cost concerns created financial barriers for both patients and healthcare systems (George et al., 2025). Cultural factors, including traditional treatment preferences and beliefs, sometimes conflicted with evidence-based approaches. Training deficiencies, particularly inadequate continuing education programmes for practicing healthcare providers, limited knowledge dissemination. Finally, poor translation of guidelines into practice at the policy implementation level hindered systematic adoption of zinc supplementation protocols (Ali et al., 2024).

METHODOLOGY

Study design and setting

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between August and September 2016 among Nigerian-trained nurses studying at Anglia Ruskin University, Chelmsford campus, United Kingdom. The study adopted a quantitative approach within a positivistic paradigm to assess the relationship between knowledge, awareness, and practice of zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management. The study population was selected because these nurses had recent training and practice experience in Nigeria while also being accessible for participation in an international university setting.

Participants and sampling

The target population comprised nurses who had trained or practiced in Nigeria and were currently pursuing further studies at Anglia Ruskin University during the 2015-2016 academic year. Inclusion criteria required current enrolment at the university and previous training or practice experience in Nigeria. Nurses who had trained or practiced exclusively outside Nigeria were excluded from the study. Sample size was calculated using the formula $n = N/1+N(e)^2$, where $N=148$ represented the total accessible population and $e=0.10$ represented the acceptable error margin. The minimum required sample size was calculated as 60 participants. This was increased to 65 to account for an anticipated 80% response rate, as well as potential non-responses or incomplete surveys. A snowball sampling strategy was employed to reach eligible participants within the geographically dispersed international student population. This approach was selected because Nigerian-trained nurses at the university were not centrally registered or easily identifiable through institutional records, and professional networks provided the most efficient mechanism for identifying and recruiting eligible participants. Initial participants were recruited from nursing and MSc Public Health programmes, who subsequently identified other eligible participants through their personal and professional networks.

Data collection instrument

Data were collected using a semi-structured electronic questionnaire developed through the Zoho Survey platform. The Zoho Survey platform was selected for several practical reasons: it provided accessible online survey functionality suitable for reaching geographically dispersed international students, offered data security features compliant with UK research ethics requirements, enabled electronic consent processes, and allowed for real-time data collection and basic analytics. The platform was adapted for this study's specific needs rather than using a pre-existing template, with questions customized based on literature review and research objectives. The questionnaire was developed in English following extensive literature review of relevant studies on zinc supplementation knowledge and practice. The instrument was designed to be self-administered and contained multiple sections addressing different aspects of the research objectives. The sociodemographic section collected information on age, gender, years of nursing experience, region of training or practice in Nigeria, and current educational programme. The awareness section assessed whether participants had heard of zinc supplementation for childhood diarrhoea and identified their sources of information about this intervention.

The knowledge section included questions assessing understanding of basic diarrhoea concepts, causative agents, complications, and treatment approaches. Specific questions addressed whether participants knew that zinc supplementation was included in current diarrhoea management protocols and whether they understood zinc's therapeutic effects in reducing diarrhoea duration and severity. Knowledge scoring was based on correct responses to these core questions, with participants classified as having adequate knowledge if they correctly answered questions about zinc inclusion in protocols and zinc's therapeutic effects or demonstrated strong agreement with these evidence-based statements.

The practice section inquired whether participants had ever used zinc supplements when treating childhood diarrhoea cases during their practice in Nigeria. Additional questions assessed perceived effectiveness of zinc supplementation using a Likert scale ranging from highly effective to highly ineffective. The questionnaire also

explored barriers to effective diarrhoea treatment and appropriate clinical management approaches including rehydration therapy and antibiotic prescription practices. The survey link was distributed through email to identified eligible participants and remained accessible for one month during August and September 2016. Participants could complete the survey at their convenience during this period.

Validity and reliability

Content validity was established through review and approval by the Faculty Research Ethics Panel of the Faculty of Medical Sciences at Anglia Ruskin University. The panel reviewed the questionnaire for appropriateness, clarity, and alignment with research objectives. The electronic questionnaire was pretested among 20 nurses in a non-study area to assess comprehension and identify any technical or interpretive difficulties. The pretest achieved a 90% response rate and feedback indicated good comprehension of all variables, with no major revisions required before final implementation.

Data analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS version 20.0 statistical software and Zoho Survey analytics platform. Descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages, means, and cross-tabulations were generated to characterise the sample and describe patterns in awareness, knowledge, and practice. Chi-square tests of independence were performed to examine associations between categorical variables including the relationship between knowledge and practice, between gender and practice, and between region and practice. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Effect sizes were considered alongside statistical significance when interpreting findings, recognising that the relatively small sample size limited statistical power to detect some associations, particularly in subgroup analyses. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was initially planned to control for potential confounding variables in the knowledge-practice relationship. However, this analysis was not conducted due to the limited sample size relative to the number of potential predictor variables, which would have resulted in an unstable regression model with unreliable parameter estimates.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Faculty Research Ethics Panel, Faculty of Medical Science, Anglia Ruskin University (Reference: CS/jc/FMSFREP/15/16 088) in March 2016, prior to data collection. All participants provided informed consent by voluntarily completing the electronic survey after being informed about the study purpose, procedures, and their rights. The information sheet explained that participation was voluntary, responses would be anonymous, data would be stored securely, and participants could withdraw at any time without penalty. No identifying information was collected, and all data were aggregated for analysis and reporting.

RESULTS

Participant characteristics

A total of 63 Nigerian-trained nurses participated in the study, yielding a response rate of 96.9% from the 65

nurses who received the survey invitation through snowball sampling. The high response rate may reflect the engaged nature of the student population and the relevance of the topic to nursing practice. The sample comprised 43 female nurses (68%) and 20 male nurses (32%), reflecting the gender distribution common in nursing education programmes. Age distribution showed that 29 participants (46%) were between 25 and 34 years, 17 participants (27%) were under 25 years, 13 participants (21%) were between 35 and 44 years, and 4 participants (6%) were 45 years and above. This age distribution indicated a predominantly younger cohort of nurses pursuing advanced education.

Professional experience varied across the sample, with 28 participants (45%) having 1 to 5 years of nursing experience, 19 participants (31%) having 6 to 10 years of experience, 9 participants (15%) having less than one year of experience, and 6 participants (10%) having more than 10 years of experience. The predominance of nurses with less than 10 years of experience suggests that participants were primarily early to mid-career professionals. Geographically, participants represented all regions of Nigeria, though distribution was uneven. The South-South region had the highest representation with 18 participants (29%), followed by the North-East region with 11 participants (17%) and the South-West region with 10 participants (16%). Other regions included the North-Central with 8 participants (13%), South-East with 7 participants (11%), North-West with 6 participants (10%), and a small number from unspecified or multiple regions. This geographic diversity provides some breadth to the sample, though the small numbers from some regions limit subgroup analysis reliability.

Awareness of zinc supplementation

Fifty-seven participants (90%) reported awareness of zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management, while 6 participants (10%) indicated they were unaware of this intervention. Gender analysis revealed that 40 of 43 female nurses (93%) and 17 of 20 male nurses (85%) were aware of zinc supplementation, suggesting no substantial gender difference in awareness levels. Sources of information about zinc supplementation varied among aware participants.

Nursing training schools represented the most common source, cited by 18 participants (32% of aware participants), indicating that formal nursing education curricula included content on zinc supplementation. Workplace settings and co-workers were the second most common source at 15 participants (27%), suggesting peer learning and workplace training played important roles. Formal training programmes were identified by 10 participants (18%), while other sources including media, seminars, and personal reading

comprised smaller proportions. Radio was the least common source at only 1 participant (2%), indicating limited reach of mass media campaigns regarding this intervention.

Knowledge assessment

Knowledge was assessed through multiple indicators including understanding of basic diarrhoea concepts, zinc's inclusion in treatment protocols, and zinc's therapeutic mechanisms and effects. Participants demonstrated strong foundational knowledge of diarrhoea definitions and management. Sixty-one participants (97%) correctly defined diarrhoea as three or more loose stools per day. Sixty participants (95%) identified bacteria as a causative agent, while 43 participants (68%) recognised viruses as the primary cause in children, indicating good understanding of the predominantly viral aetiology of childhood diarrhoea. All participants (100%) identified dehydration as a major complication of diarrhoea. Fifty-nine participants (94%) recognised electrolyte imbalance as a complication, and the same number identified death as a potential complication, demonstrating comprehensive understanding of diarrhoea severity.

Regarding treatment approaches, 51 participants (81%) identified rehydration as the most important intervention in diarrhoea management. When asked about specific treatment modalities, 62 participants (98%) mentioned oral rehydration salts, 57 participants (91%) mentioned intravenous fluids, and 57 participants (90%) mentioned zinc supplementation as appropriate treatment options, indicating widespread recognition of these evidence-based interventions.

Specific knowledge about zinc's role in diarrhoea management was assessed through two key questions. Twenty-four participants (38%) strongly agreed that zinc supplementation is included in childhood diarrhoea management protocols, while 22 participants (35%) agreed, indicating that 73% of the sample recognised zinc's inclusion in standard protocols.

However, 2 participants (3%) disagreed, and 10 participants (16%) were uncertain, suggesting some knowledge gaps regarding guideline recommendations. Regarding zinc's therapeutic role, 26 participants (41%) strongly agreed that zinc reduces diarrhoea duration and severity, while an additional proportion agreed with this statement. However, 11 participants (18%) were neutral, and 12 participants (19%) were unsure about zinc's therapeutic effects, indicating incomplete understanding of the evidence base among a substantial minority.

Overall knowledge was classified by creating a composite score based on correct responses to core knowledge questions including zinc's inclusion in protocols and understanding of therapeutic effects. Using

this scoring system, 40 participants (63%) were classified as having adequate knowledge about zinc supplementation, while 23 participants (37%) demonstrated inadequate knowledge. The 63% adequate knowledge rate indicates moderate but not optimal knowledge levels among this educated sample of nurses pursuing advanced studies.

Practice patterns and perceptions

Forty-two participants (67%) reported having used zinc supplements when treating childhood diarrhoea cases during their practice in Nigeria, while 21 participants (33%) reported never having implemented zinc supplementation in their clinical practice. This two-thirds implementation rate indicates substantial but not universal practice adoption among nurses who were aware of and knowledgeable about zinc supplementation. Perception of zinc supplementation effectiveness was assessed using a Likert scale. Nineteen participants (30%) rated zinc supplementation as highly effective, while 20 participants (31%) rated it as effective, indicating that 61% held strongly positive views. Five participants (8%) rated zinc as neither effective nor ineffective, suggesting neutrality or uncertainty. Only 2 participants (3%) rated zinc as ineffective or highly ineffective. Notably, 17 participants (27%) were uncertain about zinc's effectiveness, representing more than one quarter of the sample. Overall perception was categorized by grouping responses, revealing that 39 participants (62%) held positive perceptions about zinc supplementation effectiveness, while 24 participants (38%) had neutral, negative, or uncertain perceptions. The substantial proportion with non-positive perceptions suggests that evidence translation regarding zinc's benefits remains incomplete.

Antibiotic prescription practices

Participants were asked about antibiotic prescription for childhood diarrhoea. Only 13 participants (21%) indicated they would prescribe antibiotics for diarrhoea cases, while the majority demonstrated appropriate restraint in antibiotic use, consistent with evidence-based guidelines that most childhood diarrhoea is viral and does not benefit from antibiotics. This finding suggests good clinical reasoning regarding antibiotic stewardship in diarrhoea disease management.

Association between knowledge and practice

A Chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the association between knowledge level

(adequate versus inadequate) and practice of zinc supplementation (ever used versus never used). The analysis revealed a statistically significant association ($\chi^2=32.904$, $df=1$, $p<0.001$), indicating a strong relationship between knowledge and practice implementation. Among the 40 nurses classified as having adequate knowledge, 37 participants (93%) reported having used zinc supplements in their practice in Nigeria, while only 3 participants (7%) with adequate knowledge had never used zinc. Conversely, among the 23 nurses with inadequate knowledge, only 5 participants (22%) had used zinc supplements, while 18 participants (78%) had never implemented zinc supplementation. This pattern demonstrates that nurses with adequate knowledge were substantially more likely to have incorporated zinc supplementation into their clinical practice. The strength of this association suggests that knowledge represents a critical determinant of practice implementation, though the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference. The finding that 7% of knowledgeable nurses still had not used zinc indicates that knowledge alone is insufficient for universal implementation, while the 22% of inadequately knowledgeable nurses who had used zinc suggests that some implementation may occur through protocol adherence even without complete understanding.

Regional variations in practice

Chi-square analysis examined the association between region of training or practice in Nigeria and zinc supplementation use. No statistically significant association was found ($\chi^2=9.885$, $df=7$, $p=0.195$), indicating that regional differences did not reach statistical significance in this sample. However, descriptive examination of regional patterns revealed substantial variation in reported utilisation rates that may be clinically meaningful despite lacking statistical significance.

The South-South region showed the highest utilisation rate with 16 of 18 participants (88.9%) reporting zinc use. The North-West region had 5 of 6 participants (83.3%) reporting use. In contrast, the North-East region had the lowest rate with 4 of 11 participants (36.4%) reporting zinc use, and the North-Central region had 4 of 8 participants (50%) reporting use.

These descriptive differences, ranging from 36.4 to 88.9% across regions, represent substantial variation in practice patterns. The lack of statistical significance likely reflects insufficient statistical power due to small sample sizes within regional subgroups rather than absence of true regional differences. The small cell sizes in some regions (for example, only 6 participants from North-West) limit the reliability of these comparisons. Future research with larger samples would be needed to definitively establish whether regional differences in zinc supplementation practice exist across Nigeria.

Gender and practice relationship

Chi-square analysis examined the relationship between gender and zinc supplementation practice, revealing no significant association ($\chi^2=0.037$, $df=1$, $p=0.848$). Among female nurses, 29 of 43 participants (67%) reported using zinc supplements, while among male nurses, 13 of 20 participants (65%) reported zinc use. These virtually identical rates indicate that gender does not appear to influence zinc supplementation practice patterns in this sample.

Barriers to effective diarrhoea treatment

Participants were asked to rank various barriers to effective diarrhoea treatment in children. Responses were scored and mean scores calculated to identify the most significant barriers. Household poverty received the highest mean score of 5.76, indicating that economic constraints were perceived as the primary barrier to effective treatment. This barrier encompasses inability to afford medications, transport to healthcare facilities, and opportunity costs of seeking care.

Poor sanitation received a mean score of 5.33, ranking as the second most significant barrier. Poor sanitation contributes to high diarrhoea incidence and creates ongoing exposure risks that undermine treatment effectiveness.

Delayed treatment seeking received a mean score of 4.92, representing the third most significant barrier. Delays in seeking appropriate care often result in progression to more severe dehydration and complications. In contrast, lack of knowledge about where to seek help received a mean score of only 1.60, indicating this was perceived as the least significant barrier. This suggests that awareness of available healthcare services exists, with access and resource limitations representing greater obstacles than information gaps.

DISCUSSION

This study provides insights into knowledge, awareness, and practice patterns regarding zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management among Nigerian-trained nurses pursuing advanced education abroad in 2016. The findings reveal both encouraging trends and persistent challenges in implementing evidence-based diarrhoea management guidelines.

High awareness with practice implementation gaps

The 90% awareness rate among participating nurses represents a substantial improvement compared to

earlier Nigerian studies. Research by Omuemu et al. (2012) reported 66% awareness among healthcare providers in Benin City, Nigeria, suggesting either improvement over time or differences between this selected sample and the general nursing workforce. The high awareness in this study may reflect enhanced integration of updated diarrhoea management protocols in nursing education curricula during the early 2010s or may indicate that nurses with resources and motivation to pursue international education represent a more informed subset of the profession. However, the translation from awareness to reported practice remained incomplete, with 67% of nurses reporting having used zinc supplements during their practice in Nigeria. While this two-thirds implementation rate exceeds some earlier reports, it falls short of universal implementation despite high awareness levels. This implementation gap aligns with patterns observed globally in developing countries, where uptake of evidence-based interventions for childhood diarrhoea has been documented as slow and incomplete.

Recent international evidence supports these findings. A comprehensive analysis of Demographic and Health Survey data from 23 low- and middle-income countries demonstrated positive trends toward wider zinc adoption globally between 2010 and 2020, though substantial implementation gaps persisted across all regions (Karlsson et al., 2024). Similarly, studies from sub-Saharan Africa documented that adherence to WHO recommendations for zinc supplementation remained suboptimal even among trained healthcare providers, with factors such as supply chain issues, cost barriers, and incomplete training contributing to implementation gaps (Deichsel et al., 2023). The 33% of aware and knowledgeable nurses who had not implemented zinc supplementation suggests that barriers beyond knowledge impede practice. These may include supply chain issues affecting zinc availability, cost barriers for patients, institutional protocols that do not mandate zinc supplementation, or time constraints in busy clinical settings. The gap between knowledge and universal practice underscores that educational interventions alone are insufficient without addressing systems-level implementation barriers.

Knowledge levels and their implications

The classification of 63% of participants as having adequate knowledge about zinc supplementation presents a mixed picture. On one hand, nearly two-thirds of nurses demonstrated understanding of zinc's inclusion in diarrhoea management protocols and its therapeutic effects, indicating successful knowledge dissemination through nursing education and professional development. On the other hand, 37% inadequate knowledge among

nurses pursuing advanced degrees is concerning and suggests that knowledge gaps persist even among relatively educated healthcare providers. This 63% adequate knowledge rate among international students compares favourably with some studies from other developing countries. Research in Ethiopia reported 58% adequate knowledge among primary healthcare workers, while studies in India found variable knowledge levels depending on healthcare setting and training exposure.

However, other studies among specialized paediatric providers who received focused training reported higher knowledge levels, suggesting that targeted educational interventions can substantially improve knowledge beyond baseline levels achieved in standard nursing education. Comparative analysis with studies from other African countries reveals similar challenges. Recent research from Ethiopia in 2024 found that zinc utilisation among children with acute diarrhoea varied significantly across regions, with maternal education, previous zinc exposure, and healthcare provider knowledge playing crucial roles (Seifu et al., 2024). A multi-country study examining zinc treatment patterns across 23 nations found that knowledge gaps among healthcare providers represented a persistent barrier to implementation, though positive trends were observed in countries with sustained training initiatives (Karlsson et al., 2024).

The finding that 19% of participants were unsure about zinc's therapeutic effects and 16% were uncertain about zinc's inclusion in protocols indicates incomplete evidence translation. These knowledge gaps may reflect insufficient emphasis in nursing curricula, limited access to updated guidelines, or inadequate continuing education for practicing nurses. The variation in knowledge levels also suggests heterogeneity in nursing education quality across different training institutions in Nigeria.

The critical knowledge-practice relationship

The highly significant association between knowledge and practice ($p < 0.001$) represents one of the study's most important findings. Nurses with adequate knowledge demonstrated a 93% practice implementation rate compared to only 22% among those with inadequate knowledge. This strong relationship suggests that knowledge represents a critical, though not sole, determinant of evidence-based practice implementation. The finding that 93% of knowledgeable nurses had implemented zinc supplementation indicates that knowledge is highly predictive of practice. However, the 7% of knowledgeable nurses who had not used zinc demonstrates that knowledge alone does not guarantee implementation. Barriers such as zinc unavailability, patient inability to afford supplements, or lack of institutional support may prevent even knowledgeable

nurses from implementing evidence-based practices. Conversely, the 22% of nurses with inadequate knowledge who had used zinc suggests that some implementation occurs through adherence to institutional protocols or colleague practices even without full understanding. This highlights the potential value of systems-level interventions such as Standardised treatment protocols and clinical decision support tools that can promote evidence-based practice independent of individual provider knowledge.

International evidence from India supports these findings, demonstrating that provider knowledge is strongly associated with appropriate zinc and ORS use, though knowledge alone does not fully account for practice variations (Lamberti et al., 2015).

The knowledge-practice association supports targeted educational interventions as a strategy for improving zinc supplementation implementation. However, the persistent implementation gap even among knowledgeable nurses indicates that education must be coupled with systems-level changes addressing supply, cost, and institutional support to achieve universal implementation.

Clinical reasoning and antibiotic stewardship

The study revealed appropriate clinical decision-making patterns among participants in several domains. Only 21% indicated they would prescribe antibiotics for childhood diarrhoea, demonstrating good antibiotic stewardship and recognition that most childhood diarrhoea is viral and does not benefit from antibiotics. This finding contrasts favourably with studies from India and other settings where antibiotic over-prescription for diarrhoea remains problematic.

Recent WHO (2024) guidelines have reinforced the importance of antibiotic stewardship, discouraging antibiotic use for acute watery diarrhoea except in cases with visible blood in stool, where ciprofloxacin remains the first-line treatment (Kundu et al., 2025). The low antibiotic prescription rate may reflect successful emphasis on antimicrobial stewardship in contemporary Nigerian nursing education. However, it is important to note that this finding represents stated practice intentions rather than observed clinical behaviour, and actual practice patterns may differ. The discrepancy between zinc under-utilisation and appropriate antibiotic restraint is interesting, suggesting that some evidence-based practices are more successfully implemented than others, possibly reflecting differences in training emphasis, supply availability, or cost implications.

Barriers beyond knowledge

The identification of household poverty as the primary barrier to effective diarrhoea treatment, with a mean

score of 5.76, highlights the critical role of socioeconomic factors in healthcare access and utilisation. Even when healthcare providers possess knowledge and willingness to prescribe zinc supplementation, patient inability to afford supplements represents a fundamental implementation barrier. In Nigeria, where a substantial proportion of healthcare costs are borne out-of-pocket, the cost of zinc supplements may be prohibitive for many families despite relatively low absolute costs. Recent cost-effectiveness analyses have demonstrated that zinc supplementation represents one of the most cost-effective interventions for reducing childhood diarrhoea burden in low- and middle-income countries, with benefits far exceeding costs when scaled appropriately (Baral et al., 2020). However, these system-level economic benefits do not address immediate household affordability barriers that impede individual access.

Poor sanitation, ranked as the second most significant barrier with a mean score of 5.33, reflects the broader public health context in which diarrhoea disease management occurs. High diarrhoea incidence driven by poor water quality, inadequate sanitation infrastructure, and unhygienic conditions creates an ongoing burden that overwhelms treatment efforts. Addressing childhood diarrhoea mortality ultimately requires both improved case management and primary prevention through water, sanitation, and hygiene interventions. Delayed treatment seeking, ranked third with a mean score of 4.92, often results in children presenting with more severe dehydration and complications. Factors contributing to delay care-seeking may include distance to healthcare facilities, opportunity costs of seeking care, initial use of traditional or home remedies, and underestimation of illness severity. Early recognition and prompt treatment are critical for preventing diarrhoea-related mortality, making community education and improved healthcare access essential complements to provider knowledge.

The relatively low ranking of knowledge about where to seek help (mean score 1.60) as a barrier suggests that awareness of healthcare facilities exists, with structural and economic barriers representing greater obstacles than information gaps. This finding reinforces that improving healthcare utilisation requires addressing access, affordability, and quality rather than focusing primarily on community awareness of service locations.

Limitations and generalisability concerns

Several important limitations must be considered when interpreting these findings. Most critically, the study sample comprised Nigerian-trained nurses who were pursuing advanced education abroad in 2016. This represents a highly selected subset of the nursing profession with several distinctive characteristics that limit generalisability to nurses practicing in Nigeria. Nurses with resources and opportunities to pursue international

education likely differ systematically from the broader nursing workforce in Nigeria. They may have stronger educational backgrounds, greater exposure to updated clinical guidelines, higher socioeconomic status, better English proficiency, and greater professional ambition. Their knowledge levels and practice patterns during prior work in Nigeria may not reflect those of nurses who remain in Nigerian healthcare settings without international educational experiences.

Furthermore, the study assessed practice patterns retrospectively, asking participants to recall their zinc supplementation use during prior practice in Nigeria. Recall bias may affect accuracy of practice reporting, with participants potentially over-reporting evidence-based practices due to social desirability bias or genuinely imperfect memory of past clinical behaviours. The practice measurement also did not distinguish between occasional and consistent use, assess appropriateness of dosing when zinc was prescribed, or verify actual implementation through chart review or direct observation. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inference regarding the knowledge-practice relationship. While the strong association suggests knowledge influences practice, reverse causation is possible, with successful practice implementation reinforcing knowledge through experiential learning. Unmeasured confounding variables such as quality of training institution, workplace resources, or individual motivation may explain both knowledge and practice patterns.

The relatively small sample size of 63 participants limits statistical power, particularly for subgroup analyses such as regional comparisons. The lack of statistically significant regional differences ($p=0.195$) despite substantial descriptive variation (36.4 to 88.9% utilisation across regions) likely reflects insufficient power rather than absence of true differences. Larger samples would be needed to definitively characterise regional practice patterns. The snowball sampling approach, while necessary given the dispersed international student population, may introduce selection bias if participants recruited through social networks share similar characteristics, training backgrounds, or practice experiences. The very high response rate of 96.9% is encouraging but may partly reflect self-selection of nurses particularly interested in paediatric care or evidence-based practice. Finally, the study was conducted in 2016, and both clinical practice patterns and guideline recommendations have evolved subsequently. The assessment of knowledge based on 2016 guidelines may not reflect current knowledge needs, and reported practice patterns from participants' time in Nigeria may not represent contemporary practice.

Implications for practice improvement

Despite these limitations, the study findings have several

implications for efforts to improve zinc supplementation implementation. The strong knowledge-practice association supports targeted educational interventions as one component of comprehensive implementation strategies. Training programmes should emphasise not only theoretical knowledge about zinc's mechanisms but also practical skills including patient counselling about zinc supplementation benefits, dosing protocols, side effect management, and addressing common patient concerns or misconceptions.

However, education alone will be insufficient without addressing systems-level barriers. Ensuring consistent availability of affordable zinc supplements requires reliable procurement and distribution systems, potentially including zinc pre-positioning at health facilities and integration into essential medicines lists. Cost barriers may necessitate subsidisation programmes, insurance coverage, or bulk purchasing arrangements to make zinc accessible to low-income families.

Healthcare facilities should implement systems to support and monitor zinc supplementation adherence. Standardised treatment protocols, clinical decision support tools integrated into patient care workflows, and regular performance feedback to providers may promote consistent implementation. Quality improvement initiatives with facility-level monitoring of zinc supplementation rates could identify implementation barriers and track improvement over time.

Policy development at national and regional levels should explicitly address zinc supplementation as a priority intervention for reducing childhood diarrhoea mortality. Policies should include funding mechanisms, training requirements, performance standards, and accountability structures to ensure systematic implementation across healthcare facilities. Community engagement represents another critical component of comprehensive implementation. Even when healthcare providers prescribe zinc appropriately, patient acceptance and adherence determine actual treatment effectiveness. Community education about zinc supplementation benefits, coupled with efforts to address poverty and improve healthcare access, would support both supply-side provider implementation and demand-side family utilisation.

Contemporary context

It is important to note that since this study was conducted in 2016; both the evidence base and clinical guidelines for zinc supplementation have continued to evolve. Recent clinical trials have investigated lower-dose zinc formulations, with studies published after 2016 demonstrating that reduced doses may maintain therapeutic efficacy while minimising adverse effects such as vomiting. A landmark randomised controlled trial by

Dhingra et al. (2020) comparing 5, 10, and 20 mg daily zinc doses found that lower doses had noninferior efficacy for diarrhoea treatment and reduced vomiting compared to the standard 20 mg dose. The 2024 WHO guidelines now include a conditional recommendation for reduced zinc dosing of 5 mg daily for up to 14 days for children up to 10 years of age with acute watery or persistent diarrhoea, representing a substantial change from the 20 mg daily dose that was recommended at the time of this study (Kundu et al., 2025). This recommendation is based on a comprehensive systematic review commissioned by WHO that examined 38 randomised controlled trials, finding that lower zinc doses maintained therapeutic benefits while significantly reducing the risk of vomiting, a major barrier to zinc supplementation adherence (Ali et al., 2024).

These evolving guidelines underscore the importance of continuous professional development to ensure healthcare providers remain current with changing evidence-based recommendations. The knowledge and practice patterns documented in this 2016 study reflect the clinical context and guidelines of that period. Contemporary assessment of nursing knowledge would need to consider updated recommendations, while recognising that guideline evolution creates ongoing challenges for maintaining current knowledge among practicing clinicians. The shift toward lower-dose zinc formulations based on newer evidence also highlights the dynamic nature of evidence-based practice. Healthcare systems must develop mechanisms for efficiently disseminating guideline updates and supporting provider adaptation to changing recommendations. This represents an additional layer of complexity beyond the basic knowledge-practice gaps identified in this study.

Conclusion

This study of Nigerian-trained nurses pursuing advanced education abroad in 2016 demonstrates that awareness of zinc supplementation in childhood diarrhoea management was high at 90%, with 63% demonstrating adequate knowledge based on understanding of zinc's inclusion in treatment protocols and therapeutic effects. Two-thirds of nurses reported having implemented zinc supplementation during their practice in Nigeria. The highly significant association between knowledge and practice ($p < 0.001$) indicates that nurses with adequate knowledge were substantially more likely to implement zinc supplementation, with 93% of knowledgeable nurses reporting practice implementation compared to only 22% of nurses with inadequate knowledge. However, several important caveats must be emphasised. The study sample comprised nurses with access to international educational opportunities, representing a selected subset of the Nigerian nursing workforce that may differ

systematically from nurses practicing in Nigeria in terms of educational background, resources, and professional characteristics. Generalisability of findings to the broader nursing population is therefore limited. The practice implementation rate of 67%, while higher than some previous reports, falls short of universal implementation despite high awareness and reasonable knowledge levels among this educated sample.

The identification of household poverty as the primary barrier to effective diarrhoea treatment underscores that knowledge and practice gaps represent only part of the implementation challenge. Structural barriers including cost, supply chain issues, and socioeconomic constraints require systems-level interventions beyond individual provider education. Addressing these barriers necessitates comprehensive approaches integrating education, policy development, supply chain optimisation, financial mechanisms to ensure affordability, and community engagement.

The study was conducted in 2016, and both clinical practice patterns and evidence-based guidelines have evolved subsequently. The 2024 WHO guidelines recommend a reduced zinc dosage, marking a significant shift from the standard 20 mg daily dose used during the study period. This change highlights the need for ongoing professional development and flexible implementation strategies to keep healthcare providers up-to-date with evolving evidence and recommendations. Healthcare systems should establish efficient mechanisms for disseminating guideline updates and supporting providers in adapting to changing evidence.

The strong knowledge-practice correlation identified in this study highlights the potential impact of targeted educational interventions as one component of comprehensive implementation strategies. However, the persistence of implementation gaps even among knowledgeable nurses indicates that education alone is insufficient. Successful implementation requires multi-faceted approaches addressing knowledge gaps, systems barriers, cost constraints, supply availability, policy frameworks, and community factors simultaneously. Future research should focus on larger-scale implementation studies employing probability sampling across diverse healthcare settings and geographic regions to provide more generalizable findings. Cost-effectiveness analyses would support resource allocation decisions and policy advocacy. Implementation science research identifying effective strategies for translating guidelines into practice across varied contexts would inform intervention design.

Qualitative research exploring provider, patient, and organisational perspectives would complement quantitative findings and elucidate implementation mechanisms.

The ultimate goal remains translating scientific evidence about zinc supplementation effectiveness into improved clinical outcomes through enhanced healthcare

provider knowledge, supportive systems infrastructure, accessible and affordable zinc supplies, and comprehensive policy frameworks. As global health initiatives continue prioritising reductions in preventable childhood mortality, optimizing zinc supplementation implementation represents a critical opportunity to improve outcomes for children suffering from diarrhoea diseases in Nigeria and similar low- and middle-income settings. Despite the limitations inherent in studying a selected sample of internationally mobile nurses, this research contributes to understanding knowledge-practice gaps in zinc supplementation implementation and highlights the multifaceted nature of barriers to evidence-based practice adoption. The findings support continued emphasis on both provider education and systems strengthening to achieve the goal of universal access to evidence-based childhood diarrhoea management incorporating zinc supplementation alongside oral rehydration therapy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study findings, contemporary evidence, and recognised limitations, several recommendations emerge for improving zinc supplementation implementation in childhood diarrhoea management, recognising that these recommendations extend beyond the specific population studied to broader Nigerian healthcare contexts.

Educational interventions

Nursing education curricula should incorporate comprehensive coverage of current diarrhoea management guidelines with regular updates as evidence evolves. Pre-service nursing education should include both theoretical knowledge about zinc's mechanisms and therapeutic effects, and practical skills training in patient counselling, family education, and adherence support. The emphasis should extend beyond memorization of guidelines to understanding the evidence base and developing clinical reasoning skills that support appropriate implementation. Continuing education programmes for practicing nurses should be developed and implemented systematically, with particular focus on nurses who completed training before zinc supplementation guidelines were widely disseminated. These programmes should employ evidence-based adult learning principles including interactive formats, case-based learning, and opportunities for skills practice. Given the strong knowledge-practice association identified in this study, continuing education represents a high-yield intervention for improving implementation rates.

Competency-based assessment and certification programmes could be developed to verify provider

knowledge and skills in childhood diarrhoea management. Such programmes would provide both a quality assurance mechanism and professional development incentive, while identifying providers who require additional training support. Certification could be linked to professional advancement or practice privileges to incentivize participation and mastery.

Healthcare system strengthening

Reliable supply chain systems must be established to ensure consistent availability of zinc supplements at healthcare facilities. This requires attention to procurement planning, distribution logistics, inventory management, and forecasting to prevent stockouts that undermine provider implementation efforts. Zinc supplements should be included in essential medicines lists at all levels of the healthcare system and pre-positioned at facilities providing paediatric care. Affordability barriers require specific attention through subsidisation programmes, insurance coverage provisions, or bulk purchasing arrangements that reduce costs for families. Given the identification of household poverty as the primary treatment barrier, cost-effective mechanisms for providing zinc supplements to low-income families are essential for equitable access. Public-private partnerships might be explored to leverage pharmaceutical company resources while ensuring affordable access.

Standardised treatment protocols and clinical decision support tools should be developed and integrated into healthcare facility workflows. These tools can include treatment algorithms, standing orders, or electronic reminders that prompt providers to consider zinc supplementation for eligible patients. Such systems-level interventions can support implementation even when individual provider knowledge is incomplete, while also serving as educational reinforcement.

Quality improvement initiatives should be implemented at facility levels with regular monitoring of zinc supplementation utilisation rates, documentation practices, and patient outcomes. Performance data should be fed back to providers regularly to support continuous improvement, identify implementation barriers, and recognize successful practices. Facility-level quality improvement teams could address context-specific barriers and develop locally appropriate solutions.

Policy development and advocacy

National health policies should explicitly prioritize zinc supplementation as a key intervention for reducing childhood diarrhoea morbidity and mortality. Policies

should include clear implementation standards, funding allocations, training requirements, and accountability mechanisms. Integration of zinc supplementation targets into national health indicators and facility performance assessments would elevate priority and support systematic implementation. Professional regulatory bodies and nursing associations should incorporate zinc supplementation knowledge and skills into licensure or registration requirements, continuing professional development mandates, and scope of practice guidelines.

Professional organisations can also serve as platforms for disseminating updated guidelines and supporting peer learning networks. Advocacy efforts should target policymakers, health administrators, and international donors to secure resources and political commitment for comprehensive diarrhoea management programmes. Evidence about zinc supplementation effectiveness and cost-effectiveness should be translated into accessible formats for policy audiences, emphasising both health outcomes and economic benefits of preventing diarrhoea-related mortality and morbidity.

Research priorities

Larger-scale studies are needed to assess knowledge, practice patterns, and implementation barriers across diverse healthcare settings and geographic regions within Nigeria. Such studies should employ probability sampling to enhance generalisability and should include nurses at various career stages and practice settings. Research should examine both knowledge and observed practice behaviour, addressing the limitations of self-reported practice measurement.

Implementation science research should investigate effective strategies for translating guidelines into practice, comparing different educational approaches, systems interventions, and policy mechanisms. Research should identify context-specific barriers and facilitators, recognising that effective implementation strategies may vary across settings based on resources, infrastructure, and organisational culture. Cost-effectiveness analyses of zinc supplementation programmes would provide valuable evidence for resource allocation decisions and policy advocacy. Such analyses should consider healthcare system costs and family out-of-pocket expenditures, as well as downstream economic benefits of preventing mortality and morbidity. Comparative effectiveness research examining different zinc formulations, dosing strategies, and delivery mechanisms would inform optimal implementation approaches.

Qualitative research exploring provider perspectives, patient and family experiences, and organisational factors affecting implementation would complement quantitative studies and provide insights into implementation mechanisms. Understanding why knowledgeable

providers sometimes fail to implement zinc supplementation and what supports successful implementation in resource-constrained settings would inform intervention design. Longitudinal research tracking practice patterns over time, particularly following educational interventions or policy changes, would provide evidence about sustainability and factors supporting long-term behaviour change. Such research should also examine how healthcare systems adapt to evolving guidelines and what mechanisms support efficient dissemination and adoption of updated recommendations.

Community engagement

Community education programmes should be developed to increase family awareness of zinc supplementation benefits and appropriate care-seeking for childhood diarrhoea. Such programmes should address common misconceptions, explain the rationale for zinc supplementation, and emphasise the importance of completing the full treatment course even after symptoms improve. Community health workers could serve as key agents for delivering these messages and supporting family adherence. Engagement with traditional and religious leaders may help address cultural beliefs or practices that conflict with evidence-based diarrhoea management. Respectful dialogue that acknowledges traditional practices while introducing complementary evidence-based approaches may be more effective than direct contradiction of traditional beliefs. Integration of zinc supplementation into culturally acceptable treatment frameworks could enhance uptake. Community mobilization around broader water, sanitation, and hygiene improvements represents a complementary approach to case management. While improving clinical treatment of diarrhoea episodes is essential, primary prevention through improved sanitation infrastructure, safe water access, and hygiene behaviour change would reduce overall disease burden. Comprehensive approaches addressing both prevention and treatment are needed for substantial mortality reduction.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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